

Analysis influence of perceived complaint handling quality, customer effort, and quality of service solution to customer satisfaction and customer loyalty b2b in east java, Indonesia

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Abstract:

Fuel products, fuel handling, fleet management, and depot management are all services provided by PT Pertamina Patra Niaga. Despite today's rising rivalry, the company's position has been enhanced by more efficient methods and logical organizational techniques. PT Pertamina Patra Niaga is committed to increasing its competitiveness in the domestic and international oil and gas industries. The approach for gathering the needed data is to distribute questionnaires using Google Form to Pertamina customer service agents who satisfy the requirements as research samples until the sample size of 32 is reached. After collecting all of the data from the Google form, the data is tabulated in Excel. Full sampling was employed as the sample technique. Based on the data analysis, four of the six submitted hypotheses are accepted, while two are rejected.

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1. Introduction

Fuel products, fuel handling, fleet management, and depot management are all services provided by PT Pertamina Patra Niaga. Despite today's rising rivalry, the company's position has been enhanced by more efficient methods and logical organizational techniques. PT Pertamina Patra Niaga is committed to increasing its competitiveness in the domestic and international oil and gas industries. PT Pertamina Patra Niaga is striving to maintain its position in the highly competitive downstream oil and gas market. With more than 140 supply points throughout Indonesia, together with a responsive team that is always aware of customer needs, PT Patra Niaga aims to become an energy solution that is more accessible. In carrying out its business pattern, PT. Pertamina Patra Niaga (PPN) runs 2 patterns, namely the B2B business pattern where BBM is sold to distributors / agents / official distributors who are certified with a Distributor Certificate (SKP) from the Director General of Oil and Gas and to business entities holding general trading permits that can resell BBM from PT. Pertamina Patra Niaga to consumers/end users. The second business pattern is a business pattern that is run with a B2C process where BBM is sold directly to consumers who are BBM users/end users. These two patterns have their respective advantages and disadvantages, so they are applied as the main business pattern in the sales strategy (www.pertamina.com, downloaded on May 20, 2021). B2B run by VAT has advantages and is one of the marketing strengths of VAT. B2B has a wider reach, has the ability to generate greater profits because it can maintain the company's cash flow and the sales process is faster and more massive. With these advantages, VAT needs to prioritize and prioritize these B2B customers. VAT partners in B2B are called Agents (www.pertamina.com, downloaded on 20 May 2021). Realizing the importance of the role of agents, VAT needs to increase its competitiveness. Because there are quite a lot of VAT competitors. Besides, PT. Pertamina Patra Niaga requires strategic steps to be able to maintain its existence and position in a market that is currently increasingly developing and competitive with the entry of international companies as new competitors, for example AKR, Shell, Total, Medco, and so on. An effective and appropriate service management process is an important factor for perceived service quality across all marketing channels. Among the important factors of PCHQ are procedural justice, interactional justice, and distributive justice. Procedural justice refers to how the complainant views the procedures behind the decision making and conflict resolution carried out by the company (Choi and Choi, 2014; Lind and Tyler, 1988). A procedurally fair complaint management method is simple to use, allows consumers to decide the outcome, and is adaptable (Tax et al., 1998). Employee conduct throughout the complaint handling process, such as empathy, civility, and kindness, is referred to as interactional justice (Patterson et al., 2006; Tax et al., 1998; Vaerenbergh et al., 2012). Customers' opinions of the company's attempts to rectify the perceived flaws are referred to as distributive justice (Mayser and Wangenheim, 2013; Smith et al., 1999). Fairness is critical for consumer views of a company's service excellence when it comes to service and complaint processing. Customers who have had an unfair service experience will have an influence on their impressions of the organization and how they perceive it, resulting in customer satisfaction.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Customer Loyalty

Watson et al. (2015) argues that customer loyalty is a systematic series of behaviors from

an entity's request. Algesheimer et al. (2005) stated that customer loyalty is the availability of customers to make transactions with certain companies repeatedly to maintain a long-term commitment to a company even though there are potential benefits if moving to another company. Yang and Peterson (2004) suggest that customer loyalty can be defined as the preferences, attitudes, and behavior of the buying process towards one or more brands within a certain period of time where loyalty is the result of consumer pleasure in providing superior value from good service and good product quality. According to Herington & Weaven (2009), e-service quality is found to be related to satisfaction, and most of it was explained by the personal need dimension. According to Amin (2016), personal need has a significant effect towards customer satisfaction but the standardized path was the lowest compared to the dimension of personal need, site organization and efficiency. From these statements, we can make hypotheses that:

2.2 Customer Satisfaction

Client pleasure, according to Pham and Ahammad (2017), is one of the most essential variables in establishing customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction, according to Afthanorhan et al. (2019), is the degree of service performance quality that meets and even exceeds customer expectations. According to Adikaram et al. (2016), one of the most important factors for entrepreneurs is customer satisfaction. Consumer satisfaction is defined by Anderson et al. (1994) in Daz (2017) as a thorough evaluation based on the shopping experience and customer consumption of a product or service. Customer happiness, according to Delgado-Ballester and Munuera-Alemán (2001), has a beneficial impact on customer loyalty. If a consumer is happy, he or she is more likely to remain loyal to the firm (Makanyeza and Chikazhe, 2017). Customers who are satisfied are more likely to buy from you again (East, 1997). We can get the following hypothesis from these statements:

H6: Customer satisfaction has a considerable beneficial impact on customer loyalty.

2.3 Procedural Justice

Procedural justice, according to Tax et al. (1998), is the value of justice associated to the dependability of the complaint procedure. Procedural fairness plays an important part in determining consumer satisfaction when dealing with complaints (Bitner et al., 1990). Procedural fairness has a direct impact on determining consumer happiness and how service providers handle complaints (Schoefer and Ennew, 2004). We can get the following hypothesis from these statements:

H1: Procedural Justice has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction.

2.4 Interaction Justice

Interaction justice, defined by Tax et al. (1998) as "the value of justice felt by customers as a result of the interaction process between customers and employees while following the complaint handling procedure," is defined as "the value of justice felt by customers as a result of the interaction process between customers and employees during the complaint handling procedure." One of the communication variables, according to Goodwin and Ross (1992) in Gunawan and Purwono (2007: 3), plays a key part in the value of interactional justice and influences consumer decision-making. The honesty of employees or managers in handling complaints is felt by customers as a factor in the value of interactional justice which has a great influence on the emergence of customer satisfaction on handling. Schoefer and Ennew (2004) in evaluating the handling of customer complaints see the friendliness factor as a means to

make complaints and evaluate the handling of these complaints. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Interaction Justice improves customer satisfaction in a major way.

2.5 Distributive Justice

Distributive justice focuses on the role of 'equity', where an individual measures the fairness of an exchange by comparing their sacrifices with the results they get (Adam, 1963 in Maxham and Netemeyer, 2002). An exchange is considered fair when the equity score is proportional to the equity score obtained by other consumers (Greenberg, 1996). The outcome of distributive justice can be a refund, a discount, or other redress for a service failure. Lewis and McCann (2004) state that distributive justice is a company's offer to provide compensation for service failures which can be in the form of refunds, discounts, free coupons and other replacements in accordance with the substance of the complaint. Tax et al. (1998) also stated that compensation plays a very important role in relation to the perception of complaints. According to Sugathan et al (2018), distributive justice has a strong link to consumer happiness. According to the findings of CasadoDaz et al. (2007)'s research, distributive justice has a substantial association with customer happiness. According to MartnezTur et al. (2006), distributive fairness has a big impact on consumer satisfaction. As a result, the following theory is put forth:

H3: Distributive Justice has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction

2.6 Customer Effort

Customer effort is the amount of money and time spent or sacrificed by customers to obtain a product (Murphy and Enis, 1986). Cardozo (1965) reveals that customer effort is everything related to physical, mental, and financial resources used by customers to obtain a product. Söderlund and Sagfossen (2017) argue that customer effort is everything that is seen based on customer perceptions of everything that is sacrificed to get a product. Customer effort is the sum total of resources owned by customers including perceptions, memories, and judgments to obtain a product (Russo and Doshier, 1983). Customer effort has a substantial negative association with customer happiness, according to Sugathan et al (2018). Söderlund and Sagfossen (2017), in contrast to Sugathan et al. (2018), claim that there is a substantial link between customer effort and customer satisfaction. As a result, the following theory is put forth:

H4: Customer effort has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction.

2.7 Quality of Service Solutions

Quality of service solutions is a constant and excellent quality in delivering recommendations to clients, according to Liao (2007) and McCollough et al. (2000). Quality of service solutions, according to Goodwin and Ross (1992), Tax et al. (1998), Davidow (2003), and Bolton and Drew (1991), is service quality in terms of delivering solutions for consumers. According to Santos (2003), quality of service solutions is an overall review and assessment of consumers'

satisfaction with the company's service solutions. According to Sugathan et al (2018), the quality-of-service solutions has little bearing on customer happiness. The findings of Sugathan et al(2018) .'s study contradict those of Lee and Hsiu's (2005) study, which found that the quality of service solutions had a strong association with customer satisfaction. According to Lee (2013), there is a link between the quality-of-service solutions and client happiness. As a result, the following theory is put forth:

H5: Customer satisfaction is positively influenced by the quality-of-service solutions.

3. Hypothesis

Thus, the following hypotheses are used.

H1: Procedural Justice has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction.

H2: Interaction Justice improves customer satisfaction in a major way.

H3: Distributive Justice has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction

H4: Customer effort has a considerable beneficial impact on customer satisfaction.

H5: Customer satisfaction is positively influenced by the quality-of-service solutions.

H6: Customer satisfaction has a considerable beneficial impact on customer loyalty.

4. Method

A quantitative technique was applied in this investigation. The population is made up of all OVO users in Surabaya. Non-probability sampling was utilized, with a questionnaire serving as the primary data gathering instrument. Researchers will employ snowball sampling strategies in this study, in which they select respondents who will assist them in distributing and filling out questionnaires. According to the characteristics of respondents, 150 OVO users in Surabaya were interviewed for this study. The research model is shown below:

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Sugathan et al (2018)

5. Result

Multiple Regression was utilized to evaluate the relationships between the variables in this investigation. SPSS 22.0 was utilized as a statistical analysis tool to solve the research's problem formulation. The next stage is to undertake descriptive statistic-analysis when the surveys have been returned. In Table 1, it shows that respondents who fill out questionnaires are most of the company employees who cooperate with PT. Pertamina Patra Niaga 71.9% or 23 respondents are respondents with other positions, 3.1% or 11 respondents are respondents with finance manager positions, 12.5% or 4 respondents are respondents with operational manager positions and 12.5% or 4 respondents are respondents with purchasing manager positions. The majority of company employees who cooperate with PT. Pertamina Patra Niaga is in another positions.

Table 1 Respondent based on position

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Others	23	71.9	71.9	71.9
Financial Manager	1	3.1	3.1	75.0
Operasional Manager	4	12.5	12.5	87.5
Purchasing Manager	4	12.5	12.5	100.0
Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: own calculation, 2022

Table 2 Statistic Descriptive

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
PJ1	32	3.06	.669
PJ2	32	3.22	.608
PJ3	32	3.31	.644
PJ	32	3.1979166666666666	.485336043653
IJ1	32	3.000	.7620
IJ2	32	2.844	.8466
IJ3	32	3.28	.683
IJ	32	3.0416666666666666	.603157759756
DJ1	32	3.63	.833
DJ2	32	3.50	.718
DJ3	32	3.37	.707
DJ	32	3.5000000000000000	.616383253675
CE1	32	3.34	.787
CE2	32	3.22	.706
CE3	32	3.000	.8424
CE	32	3.1875000000000000	.610173604769
QSS1	32	3.13	.554
QSS2	32	3.19	.693
QSS3	32	3.25	.762
QSS	32	3.1875000000000000	.514572585974
CS1	32	2.719	.9240
CS2	32	3.000	.8799
CS3	32	3.062	.8400

CS	32	2.92708333333	.696814950520
CL1	32	2.906	.8561
CL2	32	2.938	.8007
CL3	32	2.938	.8007
CL	32	2.92708333333	.681208997976
Valid N (listwise)	32		

Source: own calculation, 2022

Table 2 reveals that the average score of the mean for the majority of indicators is above 3.61, indicating that all indicators of variables are considered as agreeable by all respondents. Furthermore, if the standard deviation is less than 2.0, the responses supplied by respondents are homogenous.

5.1.1 Validity Test

The statement is considered legitimate if the factor loading value is more than 0.160. All indicators utilized to estimate each variable are legitimate, according to the data validity test, because the factor loading for each indicator is more than 0.160.

I	FL	I	FL	I	FL	I	FL	I	FL				
Customer Loyalty		Customer Satisfaction		Quality of Service Solutions		Customer Effort		Distributive Justice		Interactional Justice		Procedural Justice	
C L 1	0.87 3	C S 1	0.66 9	SW C 1	0.67 0	C I 1	0.77 9	CS P 1	0.85 9	P R 1	0.79 5	AP 1	0.82 2
C L 2	0.80 0	C S 2	0.87 7	SW C 2	0.83 3	C I 2	0.75 0	CS P 2	0.77 7	P R 2	0.85 5	A P 2	0.68 6
C L 3	0.81 9	C S 3	0.83 5	SW C 3	0.78 2	C I 3	0.81 6	CS P 3	0.81 4	P R 3	0.70 1	A P 3	0.75 8

Source: own calculation

5.1.2 Reliability Test

The cronbach's alpha value is compared to the statement's reliability. If the value is more than 0.6, the statement is regarded reliable.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items
<i>Customer Loyalty</i>	0.775
<i>Customer Satisfaction</i>	0.706
<i>Quality of Service Solutions</i>	0.644
<i>Customer Effort</i>	0.683
<i>Distributive Justice</i>	0.751
<i>Interactional Justice</i>	0.689
<i>Procedural Justice</i>	0.625

Source: own calculation

Source: own calculation, 2022

Table 4 shows that variables with a Cronbach alpha value greater than 0.60 are more reliable.

As a result, it may be argued that the statements describing the variables are consistent and dependable, and that they can be utilized for further investigation.

5.1.3 Results of Multiple Regression

1. Personal Need, User Friendliness, Efficiency to E-Customer Satisfaction

The results of multiple regression are as follows:

Table 5 Multiple Regression (PJ,IJ,DJ,CE,QSS*CS)

Variable	Standardized Coefficients
<i>Procedural Justice</i>	0.071
<i>Interactional Justice</i>	0.386
<i>Distributive Justice</i>	0.077
<i>Customer Effort</i>	0.285
<i>Quality of Service Solutions</i>	0.252

Source: own calculation, 2022

From table 5, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$CS = b_1PJ + b_2IJ + b_3DJ + b_4CE + b_5QSS$$

$$CS = 0.071.PJ + 0.386.IJ + 0.077.DJ + 0.285.AP + 0.252.QSS$$

5.1.4 Results of Simple Regression

1. Customer Satisfaction to Customer Loyalty

The results of simple regression are as follows:

Table 6 Simple Regression Result (CS*CL)

Variable	Standardized Coefficients
<i>Customer Satisfaction</i>	0.774

Source: own calculation, 2022

From table 6, the regression equation can be written as follows:

$$CL = b_6CS$$

$$CL = 0.774.CS$$

5.1.5 F-test

According to SPSS calculations, the significance of F test values in model 1 and model 2 are 0.000, implying that the three independent factors influence the dependent variable considerably.

5.1.6 t-test

The findings obtained are four acceptable hypotheses and two rejected hypotheses, as shown in tables 5 and 6. Interactional fairness affects customer satisfaction, customer effort affects customer satisfaction, quality of service solutions affects customer satisfaction, and customer contentment affects customer loyalty. Meanwhile, there was no link identified between procedural justice and customer happiness, and there was no link established between distributive justice and customer contentment.

5.1.7 Final Result

There are four acceptable hypotheses and two rejected hypotheses among the six examined. The first hypothesis proposes that procedural fairness has no bearing on consumer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is unaffected by procedural justice, yet it is positively

affected. The t test supports this hypothesis, with a significance value of 0.271 (more than 0.05), indicating that it is not accepted. The findings of this study back with recent research by Sugathan et al. (2018), which found that procedural justice had little impact on consumer satisfaction. Because PT Pertamina's standard operating procedures (SOP) are similar to those of rival corporations such as Shell, Petronas, and others in serving commercial companies in Indonesia, this theory is rejected. Although procedural justice is only marginally related to customer satisfaction, when tested together (F test), Procedural Justice (PJ), Interactional Justice (IJ), Distributive Justice (DJ), Customer Effort (CE), and Quality of Service Solutions (QSS) have a significant effect on customer satisfaction (CS) with a significance value of 0.05, which is 0.000 and is declared significant. Interactional fairness, according to the second theory, has a substantial impact on consumer happiness. The t test supports this hypothesis, with a significance value of 0.001 (less than 0.05), indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. The findings of this study back up previous research by Sugathan et al. (2018), who found that interactional justice has a significant relationship with customer satisfaction, and MartinezTur et al. (2006), who found that interactional justice has a significant relationship with customer satisfaction but is not more significant than distributive justice. Employees of a collaboration firm PT Pertamina customer service PT Pertamina have strong performance, high performance, stability, and substantial differences from rival companies, which is why this variable is approved. The interactional justice variable has a considerable influence on consumer satisfaction as a result of this. The third hypothesis is that distributive justice has a favorable influence on customer satisfaction but no substantial effect on customer satisfaction. The t test supports this hypothesis, with a significance value of 0.145 (more than 0.05), indicating that it is not accepted. The findings of this study back with prior research by MartinezTur et al. (2006), who found that while interactional justice has a considerable impact on customer satisfaction, it is not as important as distributive justice. Because information control by all parties in PT Patra Pertamina's firm exhibits parallels to rival corporations such as Shell, Petronas, and others in supplying commercial companies in Indonesia, this hypothesis is rejected. Although partially distributive justice has no effect on customer satisfaction (CS), when tested together (F test), Procedural Justice (PJ), Interactional Justice (IJ), Distributive Justice (DJ), Customer Effort (CE), and Quality of Service Solutions (QSS) have a significant effect on customer satisfaction (CS) with a significance value of 0.05, which is 0.000 and is declared significant. Customer effort has a major impact on customer satisfaction, according to the fourth hypothesis. The t test supports this hypothesis, with a significance value of 0.002 (less than 0.05), indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. The findings of this study back with previous research by Söderlund and Sagfossen (2017), which found a link between consumer effort and satisfaction. This variable is acceptable because PT Pertamina's customer service has adequate work experience to deliver good results, is responsive in delivering replies, and is more efficient than its rivals. As a result, in conjunction with PT Pertamina, the customer effort variable has a substantial impact on customer satisfaction for corporate personnel. Customer satisfaction is influenced by the quality of service solutions, according to the fifth hypothesis. The t-test supports this hypothesis, with a significant value of 0.006 (less than 0.05), indicating that the hypothesis is accepted. The findings of this study back with previous research by Lee and Hsiu (2005), who found a link between the quality of service solutions and customer happiness.

According to Lee (2013), there is a link between the quality of service solutions and client happiness. This variable is acceptable because PT Pertamina provides frequent training to customer service officers so that they may deliver better support to consumers. The reason this variable is accepted is that PT Pertamina has provided periodic training to customer service officers so that they can serve customers more optimally. This causes the variable quality of

service solutions to have a significant effect on customer satisfaction for agents collaborating with PT Pertamina. Client pleasure has a major impact on customer loyalty, according to the sixth hypothesis. This hypothesis is supported by a t-test with a significance value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), implying that it is accepted. The findings of this study back up earlier research by Delgado-Ballester and Munuera-Alemán (2001), who found that customer satisfaction had a beneficial impact on customer loyalty. If a consumer is happy, he or she is more likely to remain loyal to the firm (Makanyeza and Chikazhe, 2017). Customers who are satisfied are more likely to buy from you again (East, 1997). The customer loyalty variable is made up of the customer satisfaction variable, which has a regression coefficient of 0.774 and is the variable that has the largest effect on customer loyalty. This shows that the more customers are satisfied with PT Pertamina's customer service, the more customers are satisfied with the best service from PT. Pertamina, the higher customer loyalty to PT. Pertamina will be, and customers will want to make purchases at PT Pertamina, continue to cooperate with PT Pertamina, and have no desire to switch to other companies in the future.

6. Discussion

According to the findings, procedural justice theory, interactional justice, distributive justice, customer effort, and the quality of service solutions are all factors that must be addressed in order to entice consumers to become loyal to PT Pertamina. As a result, the management implications should be more concentrated on these factors. Customer satisfaction, according to the conclusions of this study, has the biggest impact on customer loyalty to PT Pertamina. The regression weight of the causal link between customer pleasure and customer loyalty demonstrates this. As a result, this backs up the theoretical evidence that customer pleasure affects customer loyalty (Delgado-Ballester and Munuera-Alemán) (2001). The managerial implications of these findings can be made based on the theory that has been developed as follows:

First, procedural justice is not one of the important variables that affect the level of customer satisfaction, this is because procedural justice does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction so it does not become the focus of increasing customer satisfaction, so the indicators used in this variable are not a priority in determining customers. satisfaction. But there is nothing wrong if PT. Pertamina to be able to improve these indicators by making improvements to the Go Customer application that has been developed by PT Pertamina, but has not been maximized until now. Thus, it will certainly be very helpful in the self-reporting process by customers. Another way that can be done is to improve the call center service 135 which has a function as a voice of customer which operates 24/7. Then, it is no less important that PT. Pertamina is to socialize and distribute guidebooks for handling problems that often occur in the field for agents who cooperate with PT Pertamina. In addition, PT Pertamina is also required to have an expert team to answer and help deal with any problems that may occur

Second, interaction justice is one of the important variables that affect the level of customer satisfaction of PT. Pertamina. The way to improve these indicators is by providing regular and scheduled training to employees so that they can maximize the performance of customer service officers. Another way that can be done is for PT. Pertamina to be able to improve this indicator by always providing the best service to customers under any conditions, and ensuring that it always provides solutions to every customer when a customer has a problem, for example by providing speech training on a regular basis to every employee who will serve

agents either directly or indirectly. live. Then the thing that is no less important that needs to be done by PT. Pertamina is a customer service service that can maintain confidentiality and high service quality and meet the expectations of every agent equally. Third, distributive justice is not one of the important variables that affect the level of customer satisfaction, this is because distributive justice does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction so that it does not become the focus of increasing customer satisfaction, so the indicators used in this variable are not a priority in determining customers. satisfaction. But there is nothing wrong if PT. Pertamina to be able to improve these indicators by having a minimum service standard that ensures every customer gets the same rights in every service by PT Pertamina. Another way that can be done is PT. Pertamina in order to be able to improve complaint handling services by customer service by determining service standards and ensuring all services follow the same standards. Fourth, customer effort is one of the important variables that affect the level of customer satisfaction of PT. Pertamina. The way to improve these indicators is to always provide the best service to customers, especially when customers experience problems. With the customer effort, customers feel more familiar with PT. Pertamina and of course this makes customers more trust in PT. Pertamina. Another way that can be done is by educating customers related to the services at PT. Pertamina and provide an implementation manual for making complaints to make it easier for customers to solve existing problems, especially at the stages of making a complaint. Then the thing that is no less important that needs to be done by PT. Pertamina by attaching a contact service sticker

Research Limitation

Connecting the aspects that impact consumer loyalty depending on income level, age, and gender can lead to more study. Future research can broaden the scope of respondents to be researched or perform research in areas other than the present study, resulting in a more comprehensive picture of customer loyalty.

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